

The Past as It (Virtual) Really Was? Immersive VR Applications as a New Medium of Collective Memory: Authenticity, Plausibility, Trust

Conference Paper, Berlin Program Summer Workshop 2024, FU Berlin, June 26-27, 2024

Autor: Roman Smirnov, Ruhr University Bochum, Germany, roman.smirnov@rub.de

Keywords: virtual reality, public history, historical authenticity, collective memory, new media

Introduction

The history of memory cultures knows many examples of how a media format has decisively influenced a fragment of collective memory. The perceptions of most people in the post-Soviet space about Napoleon's Russian campaign are largely shaped by Leo Tolstoy's novel "War and Peace." The perceptions of the German-speaking mass audience about Empress Elisabeth of Austria are based on the film series "Sisi" starring Romy Schneider. The perceptions of many people around the world about medieval Assassins are based on the video game "Assassin's Creed," which has become part of global memory culture (Gier, 2019, p. 79). All these are examples of how memory media operate (Dorr et al., 2019). These examples show that to have a significant influence on the memory of large collectives, history-related memory media must, first, be popular and, second, plausible. Due to their popularity, they reach a large number of people and spread within collectives, and due to plausibility, they generate trust in the content, which represents a certain image of the past.

The digital turn (Santana, 2022) brings to the forefront new memory media, among which are history-related immersive VR applications, consumed through head mounted displays, allowing for complete optical immersion (Nachtigall et al., 2022). Developers of history-related immersive VR applications are viewed as developer-historians (Giere, 2019), capable of influencing collective memory and the collective view of the past. Thus, developers engage in what is referred to in the public history literature as "doing history" (Samida et al., 2016, p. 4).

The competitive advantage of immersive VR applications over more traditional (less immersive) digital media is that they can provide more enjoyment, emotional engagement (Frentzel-Beyme & Krämer, 2023), and empathy (Barbot & Kaufman, 2020). These technological features can lend more plausibility to the constructed representation of the past, increase trust in it, and reduce the audience's critical perception. However, following the logic of the entertainment industry, developers of popular historical digital products often neglect

aspects such as the appropriate balance of human and technical realism, the moderate implementation of simulated heroism (Wackerfuss, 2013), or the critical examination of the theme of dominance (Holdenried & Trépanier, 2013, p. 111) in the self-other dichotomy. An example of this is the game "Sniper Elite VR," dedicated to the Italian front in World War II, which became one of the most downloaded VR games in the European PlayStation Store in 2022 (PlayStation Blog, 2023). In Sniper Elite VR, the dominance over the enemies and the simulated heroism manifest in the protagonist, initially an inexperienced Italian resistance fighter, single-handedly annihilating hordes of Nazi soldiers and officers from the first level. While human realism remains on the sidelines, the game's technical realism, especially regarding the reconstruction of firearms, takes clear priority for the developers, lending the game high (selective) historical authenticity (Salvati & Bullinger, 2013, p. 157).

Furthermore, history-related immersive VR apps tend not to provide users with opportunities for reflection and critical perception of the reconstructed image of the past (Lewers & Frentzel-Beyme, 2023, p. 403). Simply put, the apps often lack integrated didactic materials that explain how the past is reconstructed in immersive VR, how developers deal with categories such as authenticity and plausibility, and to what extent virtual reality corresponds to the "actual past."

All this makes history-related immersive VR applications a challenge for public history (Bunnenberg, 2018) and creates space for discussion around the following questions: Can immersive VR media influence memory about certain moments of history as strongly as some of the earlier media formats? Are immersive VR media a factor that significantly changes the mechanisms of the emergence and consumption of digital memory culture? How and to what extent will virtual realities influence how global society remembers the past?

This article analyzes the strategies employed in history-related immersive VR content to ensure historical authenticity (Schweppenstette, 2020, p. 66), which is a key category in the conversation about the plausibility and trust generated by this type of memory media. The complexity of understanding historical authenticity in virtual reality lies in the absence of a material component, i.e., a physical object with its aura, such as a classic museum exhibit, rendering many traditional notions of authenticity as irrelevant, such as originality and genuineness of historical artifacts (Schwan, 2022, p. 540). However, descriptions of history-related digital products promise historical authenticity to attract audience attention (Bunnenberg, 2017, p. 120). Such marketing tactics can be called history-as-brand (Schwarz, 2020, p. 25), with history-related digital products selling themselves by offering users a certain fragment of history that users want to experience. The success of reconstructing the atmosphere of the past (Zimmermann, 2018, p. 84) depends precisely on the degree of

historical authenticity, for which many users download (and in the case of commercial content, also purchase) history-related immersive VR apps.

Within the framework of this article, historical authenticity in immersive VR is primarily understood as a sense of credibility (Zimmermann, 2018, p. 49): the more authentic the VR app, the less it conflicts with the user's historical consciousness (Lewers & Frentzel-Beyme, 2023, p. 408), and the more the user believes that the presented depiction of the past corresponds to the actual past, to how "it really was." In other words, the more authentic the app, the more credible it is to the audience, creating greater trust in the representation of the past and a stronger plausibility illusion (Buchner & Aretz, 2020, p. 200).

Methodology

As part of my PhD research project initiated in July 2023, which focuses on the influence of immersive VR technologies on memory culture and historical consciousness, the compilation of a database of history-related immersive VR apps was started (Smirnov, 2024). Both interactive VR games and non-interactive 360-degree videos are considered. Currently, the database, based on platforms such as the Oculus Store, PlayStation Store, Steam, Pico Store, Viveport, YouTube VR, Veer, Google Play, and others, comprises over 240 titles (as of May 2024). Notably, more than 40% of the identified apps represent the 20th century, making it by far the most popular epoch. Approximately 10% of all apps focus on World War II, the most popular theme. This proportion resembles the situation in the world of history-related video games, where there is also an imbalance between historical epochs and themes, with the 20th century and World War II dominating (Rochat, 2020, p. 12).

For a qualitative analysis of strategies ensuring historical authenticity, a phenomenological approach was chosen, and a representative sample of 23 history-related immersive VR apps from the described database was compiled. This selection is based on seven criteria:

- Geographic diversity: The selected apps must originate from at least eight countries on at least four continents.
- Diversity of epochs and themes: The selected apps must cover at least four different epochs and eight different historical themes.
- Diversity of locations: The narrative of the selected apps must take place in at least eight different countries.

- Appropriate duration: The total (game) duration of the selected apps should not significantly exceed 50 hours.
- Diverse interactivity levels: The selection must include both interactive VR games and non-interactive immersive videos.
- Diverse objectives: The selection should include apps serving both educational purposes (didactics and histotainment) and entertainment purposes.
- Diverse functions: The selection must include apps performing each of the three following functions typical for history-related immersive VR content. Function 1 - Conveying visual atmosphere; Function 2 - Conveying personal perspective; Function 3 - Conveying experiences with material objects.

The resulting selection of apps is as follows:

Title	Function	Epoch/Associated modern countries/Historical theme	Purpose/ Interactivity level/Approximate duration	Studio (Country)
Accused #2: Walter Sisulu (arte, n.d.a)	2	20th century/South Africa/Apartheid	Didactics and histotainment/Immersive (not interactive) video/15 minutes	La Générale de Production, ARTE (France)
Al Zubarah (Meta, 2018a)	1	Early modern period, long 19th century, 20th century/Qatar/Reconstruction of Al Zubarah Fort	Didactics and histotainment/Interactive VR game/60 minutes	SaPhiR Prod. (Tunisia)
Anne Frank House VR (anne frank house, n.d.)	1, 2	20th century/Germany, Netherlands/Holocaust, World War II	Didactics and histotainment/Interactive VR game/30 minutes	Vertigo Games (Netherlands)
Apollo 11 VR (Meta, 2016)	1, 2, 3	20th century/USA/The moon landing 1969	Didactics and histotainment/Interactive VR game/45 minutes	Immersive VR Education Ltd. (Ireland)

Assassin's Creed Nexus VR (Ubisoft, 2023)	1, 2, 3	Ancient history, early modern period/Greece, Italy, USA/Peloponnesian War, Republic of Venice, American Revolutionary War	Entertainment/Interactive VR game/900 minutes	Ubisoft (France)
Battle of Red Cliffs VR (Steam, 2017a)	1, 3	Ancient history/China/Three Kingdoms period	Entertainment/Interactive VR game/60 minutes	WISECAT (China)
Chernobyl VR Project (The Farm 51, 2016)	1, 2	20th century/Ukraine/Chernobyl nuclear disaster	Didactics and histotainment/Interactive VR game/60 minutes	The Farm 51 (Poland)
Easter Rising: Voice of a Rebel (BBC, 2017)	2	20th century/Ireland, UK/Easter Rising in Ireland 1916	Didactics and histotainment/Immersive (not interactive) video/15 minutes	BBC (UK)
Eye of the Owl - Hieronymus Bosch VR (Viveport, 2016)	1	Middle Ages/Netherlands/Work and biography of Hieronymus Bosch	Didactics and histotainment/Interactive VR game/15 minutes	VRX (USA)
Gladiatoren im Kolosseum (ZDF, 2017)	1	Ancient history/Italy/Gladiator fights in ancient Rome	Didactics and histotainment/Immersive (not interactive) video/15 minutes	ZDF, FaberCourtial (Germany)
Gladius (Sidequest, 2020)	1, 3	Ancient history/Italy/Gladiator fights in ancient Rome	Didactics and histotainment/Interactive VR game/60 minutes	Virtual Age (Spain)
Historium VR - Relive the history of Bruges (Steam, 2016)	1	Middle Ages/Belgium/Reconstruction of medieval Bruges	Didactics and histotainment/Interactive VR game/20 minutes	Sevenedge Interactive Media (Belgium)
Meet the Miner - WDR VR Bergwerk (Steam, 2018)	1, 2, 3	20th century/Germany/Mining history	Didactics and histotainment/Interactive VR game/15 minutes	Aesir Interactive, WDR (Germany)
Peaky Blinders: The King's Ransom (Peaky Blinders: The	1, 2, 3	20th century/UK/Underworld in Britain in the 1920s	Entertainment/Interactive VR game/60 minutes	Maze Theory Limited (UK)

King's Ransom, n.d.)				
Sniper Elite VR (Rebellion, 2021)	1, 2, 3	20th century/Germany, Italy, UK/Second World War	Entertainment/Interactive VR game/600 minutes	Rebellion (UK)
Titanic VR (Meta, 2018b)	1, 2, 3	20th century/UK, USA et al./History of the Titanic	Didactics and histotainment/Interactive VR game/60 minutes	Immersive VR Education Ltd. (Ireland)
Traveling While Black (Meta, 2019a)	1, 2	20th century/USA/Racism in the USA	Didactics and histotainment/Immersive (not interactive) video/20 minutes	Felix & Paul Studios (Canada)
Verdammt zu spielen (arte, n.d.b)	1	Early modern period/Belgium/Artworks of Pieter Bruegel the Elder	Didactics and histotainment/Immersive (not interactive) video/5 minutes	Andrés Jarach, ARTE France (France)
Visby Archer (Meta, 2019b)	1, 3	Middle Ages/Denmark, Sweden/Battle of Visby 1361	Entertainment/Interactive VR game/60 minutes	Disir Productions (Sweden)
VR Battleship YAMATO (Steam, 2017b)	1	20th century/Japan/Navy of the Second World War	Didactics and histotainment/Interactive VR game/40 minutes	Kanda Technologies (Japan)
Warplanes: Battles over Pacific (Meta, 2022)	3	20th century/Japan, USA/Air Force of the Second World War	Entertainment/Interactive VR game/60 minutes	Home Net Games (Poland)
War Remains (War Remains, 2021)	1, 2	20th century/France, Germany, UK, USA/First World War	Didactics and histotainment/Immersive (not interactive) video/20 minutes	Flight School (USA)
Was wollten Sie in Berlin?! (IntoVR, 2017)	1, 2	20th century/Germany/Repression in the GDR, Stasi	Didactics and histotainment/Immersive (not interactive) video/10 minutes	IntoVR (Germany)

Results

It is noteworthy that to start all selected apps, one VR headset, such as the Oculus Quest 2, one of the most popular models on the market, was not sufficient. At least one additional headset, such as the HTC Vive VR, which works in conjunction with a stationary PC, was required. From the users' perspective, the current market situation appears to be such that there is no headset that would allow testing all immersive history-related VR apps at once. This situation can be compared to the desktop (less immersive) console video game market: none of the current flagship gaming consoles allows running all popular video games, and users have to deal with exclusive games for PS5, Xbox Series S/X, and other consoles.

In the context of the analyzed selection, two technological aspects deserve mention. First, in *Assassin's Creed Nexus VR*, in addition to immersive VR technology, mixed reality technology is also used. The player sees the physical reality (in black and white) through the cameras of the VR headset, and a transparent menu interface appears above the physical reality, reminiscent of futuristic science fiction movies. Before starting each level, a "secure connection" must be established with the Animus time machine in mixed reality mode by solving a puzzle, arranging elements in a three-dimensional cube in a specific order. Second, in *Warplanes: Battles over Pacific*, there is a multiplayer mode, which is rare for VR games. History-related immersive VR apps largely remain individual experiences in the current phase of market development, partly due to the technical peculiarities of VR headsets and partly due to the relatively low prevalence of history-related immersive VR content.

During the non-content analysis, it was noted that the market descriptions of most selected apps contain promises of historical authenticity. Developers promise historical authenticity through:

- Reconstruction/recording of historical locations (5 titles): *Anne Frank House VR*, *Chernobyl VR Project*, *Gladiatoren im Kolosseum*, *Traveling While Black*, *Visby Archer*.
- Personalization (Bergmann, 2000), i.e., the introduction of known historical figures into the narrative, which is also characteristic of many pop-culture desktop (less immersive) video games (Reisner, 2013, p. 251) (3 titles): *Anne Frank House VR*, *Assassin's Creed Nexus VR*, *Eye of the Owl - Hieronymus Bosch VR*.

- Reconstruction of historical technology and weapons (3 titles): Sniper Elite VR, VR Battleship YAMATO, Warplanes: Battles over Pacific.
- Original audio recordings (2 titles): Accused #2: Walter Sisulu, Easter Rising: Voice of a Rebel. Such use of historical audio materials in immersive VR can be seen as an example of transmedialization, i.e., enhancing the effects of one medium through the implementation of other media (Zimmermann, 2018, p. 55).
- Implementation of contemporary witnesses (2 titles): Chernobyl VR Project, Was wollten Sie in Berlin?!. This strategy of ensuring historical authenticity gained popularity on television in the 1970s (Sabrow, 2022, p. 556). Contemporary witnesses not only contribute to the authenticity of the historical narrative but also increase the level of emotionalization, as they usually convey personal experiences and feelings (Schmidt, 2011, p. 49), as well as their moral judgments (Schmidt & Voges, 2011, p. 11).
- Perspective of a participant in historical events (2 titles): War Remains, Was wollten Sie in Berlin?!. The ability for perspective-taking through the reconstruction of an ego-perspective is considered one of the main didactic advantages of immersive VR media (Mulders, 2024, p. 39), reinforcing the understanding of immersive VR technology as the ultimate empathy machine (Barbot & Kaufman, 2020).
- Reconstruction of historical rituals (1 title): Gladiatoren im Kolosseum.
- Use of historical documents in the development of VR production (1 title): Was wollten Sie in Berlin?!
- Reconstruction of famous artworks (1 title): Eye of the Owl - Hieronymus Bosch VR.
- Reconstruction of historical events (1 title): Battle of Red Cliffs VR.

In turn, historical authenticity in the selected apps is ensured through the following strategies:

- Reconstruction of historical costumes and uniforms (12 titles): Apollo 11 VR, Assassin's Creed Nexus VR, Battle of Red Cliffs VR, Gladiatoren im Kolosseum, Gladius, Meet the Miner - WDR VR Bergwerk, Peaky Blinders: The King's Ransom, Sniper Elite VR, Traveling While Black, Visby Archer, VR Battleship YAMATO, Was wollten Sie in Berlin?!

- Characteristic sounds and other elements of soundscape design (Tang & Wei, 2022, p. 40) (11 titles): Anne Frank House VR, Apollo 11 VR, Assassin's Creed Nexus VR, Battle of Red Cliffs VR, Chernobyl VR Project, Gladiatoren im Kolosseum, Gladius, Peaky Blinders: The King's Ransom, Sniper Elite VR, Visby Archer, Warplanes: Battles over Pacific. For example, in Anne Frank House VR, while moving through the reconstruction of the Frank family's hiding place in Amsterdam, one can hear creaking floors and doors or the sounds of passing airplanes and city life behind closed windows.
- Personalization (10 titles): Accused #2: Walter Sisulu, Anne Frank House VR, Assassin's Creed Nexus VR, Battle of Red Cliffs VR, Chernobyl VR Project, Eye of the Owl - Hieronymus Bosch VR, Gladiatoren im Kolosseum, Peaky Blinders: The King's Ransom, Titanic VR, Was wollten Sie in Berlin?!. For example, in Assassin's Creed Nexus VR, the player encounters Leonardo da Vinci in several levels, rescues him from bandits, and even visits his workshop.
- Reconstruction/recording of famous historical locations (10 titles): Al Zubarah, Anne Frank House VR, Assassin's Creed Nexus VR, Chernobyl VR Project, Gladiatoren im Kolosseum, Historium VR - Relive the history of Bruges, Peaky Blinders: The King's Ransom, Traveling While Black, Visby Archer, Was wollten Sie in Berlin?!
- Reconstruction of historical technology (8 titles): Apollo 11 VR, Easter Rising: Voice of a Rebel, Meet the Miner - WDR VR Bergwerk, Peaky Blinders: The King's Ransom, Sniper Elite VR, VR Battleship YAMATO, Warplanes: Battles over Pacific, War Remains. This includes military objects, such as combat aircraft in Warplanes: Battles over Pacific, as well as non-military objects, such as mining equipment in Meet the Miner - WDR VR Bergwerk.
- Reconstruction of everyday objects and interiors (6 titles): Anne Frank House VR, Assassin's Creed Nexus VR, Meet the Miner - WDR VR Bergwerk, Peaky Blinders: The King's Ransom, Sniper Elite VR, Was wollten Sie in Berlin?!. For example, in Was wollten Sie in Berlin?!, a typical interior of a solitary cell for political prisoners in late GDR is reconstructed.
- Reconstructed dialogues and replicas (5 titles): Anne Frank House VR, Sniper Elite VR, Titanic VR, VR Battleship YAMATO, Was wollten Sie in Berlin?!. While it is

not exactly known what Captain Edward John Smith of the Titanic said to bewildered passengers being loaded into lifeboats, in Titanic VR, players can hear scripted and professionally voiced lines of the captain directing the evacuation from the ship.

- Implementation of archived video recordings (5 titles): Apollo 11 VR, Chernobyl VR Project, Meet the Miner - WDR VR Bergwerk, Traveling While Black, War Remains.
- Reconstruction of weapons (5 titles): Assassin's Creed Nexus VR, Gladius, Peaky Blinders: The King's Ransom, Sniper Elite VR, Visby Archer. This includes both melee weapons, such as an indigenous tomahawk in Assassin's Creed Nexus VR, and firearms like the Gewehr 98 rifle in Sniper Elite VR.
- Imitation of old documents (4 titles): Assassin's Creed Nexus VR, Peaky Blinders: The King's Ransom, Sniper Elite VR, Visby Archer. For instance, in the opening scene of Sniper Elite VR, players encounter an old diary of the protagonist, an Italian resistance fighter. This diary mimics the main historical source on which the game's plot is based.
- Professional and expert voice-over narration (4 titles): Chernobyl VR Project, Easter Rising: Voice of a Rebel, Gladiatoren im Kolosseum, Historium VR - Relive the history of Bruges.
- Implementation of archived photos (3 titles): Anne Frank House VR, Easter Rising: Voice of a Rebel, Titanic VR.
- Reconstruction of famous artworks (3 titles): Assassin's Creed Nexus VR, Eye of the Owl - Hieronymus Bosch VR, Verdammt zu spielen. Assassin's Creed Nexus VR includes paintings and sketches by Leonardo da Vinci, which can be seen in his workshop. Eye of the Owl - Hieronymus Bosch VR and Verdammt zu spielen involve the paintings "The Garden of Earthly Delights" and "Children's Games" respectively, around which the narratives of these VR experiences are built.
- Implementation of contemporary witnesses (3 titles): Chernobyl VR Project, Easter Rising: Voice of a Rebel, Traveling While Black.
- Implementation of archived audio recordings (2 titles): Accused #2: Walter Sisulu, Easter Rising: Voice of a Rebel.

- Imitation of speech characteristics, accents, dialects (2 titles): Meet the Miner - WDR VR Bergwerk, Peaky Blinders: The King's Ransom. In Meet the Miner - WDR VR Bergwerk, miners speak in Ruhrdeutsch, a dialect of German characteristic of the working class in the Ruhr area, the largest coal mining region in Germany in the 20th century. In Peaky Blinders: The King's Ransom, some characters speak in the Brummie dialect, a variety of English characteristic of Birmingham, where the main events of this VR game take place.
- Repetition of famous visual motifs (2 titles): Titanic VR, War Remains. For example, one moment in Titanic VR strongly recalls the famous iconic engraving "Titanic Sinking" (1912) by Willy Stöwer.
- Atmosphere of a scientific expedition (1 title): Titanic VR. Placing the player in the position of a scientist-researcher who descends to the Titanic in a bathyscaphe adds an element of scientific plausibility to the gameplay and gives the game information the appearance of reliable scientific facts.
- Implementation of archive posters (1 title): Easter Rising: Voice of a Rebel.
- Implementation of old newspapers (1 title): Warplanes: Battles over Pacific.

The analyzed history-related immersive VR apps can be ranked according to the breadth of applied strategies ensuring historical authenticity:

- Wide spectrum (7 or more historical authenticity strategies): Assassin's Creed Nexus VR, Peaky Blinders: The King's Ransom, Sniper Elite VR.
- Medium spectrum (3-6 historical authenticity strategies): Anne Frank House VR, Apollo 11 VR, Battle of Red Cliffs VR, Chernobyl VR Project, Easter Rising: Voice of a Rebel, Gladiatoren im Kolosseum, Gladius, Meet the Miner - WDR VR Bergwerk, Traveling While Black, Visby Archer, VR Battleship YAMATO, War Remains, Warplanes: Battles over Pacific, Was wollten Sie in Berlin?!
- Narrow spectrum (no more than 2 historical authenticity strategies): Accused #2: Walter Sisulu, Al Zubarah, Eye of the Owl - Hieronymus Bosch VR, Historium VR - Relive the history of Bruges, Verdammt zu spielen.

Discussion

In analyzed apps, more historical authenticity strategies are used than stated in their descriptions. If there were a total of 10 mentions of such strategies in the descriptions, then 20 strategies were discovered in the actual immersive VR content. The most popular strategies for ensuring historical authenticity, namely reconstruction of historical costumes and uniforms together with characteristic sounds and other elements of soundscape design, are not mentioned in the descriptions of the selected apps. This is most likely because these strategies are perceived as something self-evident and indispensable for contemporary history-related audiovisual content.

At the same time, the most popular historical authenticity promises in the descriptions of analyzed VR apps, namely reconstruction/recording of historical locations, personalization, and reconstruction of historical technology and weapons, are also among the most frequent strategies for ensuring historical authenticity in the sample. It can be cautiously concluded that for both developers and users of immersive VR apps, historical authenticity in such content is primarily associated with these three elements.

In the analyzed selection, there is not a single app that contains at least half, that is, 10 out of 20 highlighted strategies for ensuring historical authenticity. This is partly explained by the fact that different strategies are suitable for representing different historical epochs and themes. If the reconstruction of recognizable historical places and buildings is an almost universal approach, then, for example, using interviews with contemporary witnesses or archival audio and video recordings obviously would not be suitable for representing Ancient Athens or Venice during the time of Leonardo da Vinci. In this context, it is logical that the greatest number of potential authenticity strategies are available to developers of apps dedicated to recent history, that is, the period that has been reflected in various audiovisual media sources that can be integrated into contemporary digital history-related content.

Within the analyzed selection, the most strategies for ensuring authenticity are implemented in the entertainment blockbusters *Assassin's Creed Nexus VR*, *Peaky Blinders: The King's Ransom*, and *Sniper Elite VR*. These apps are also the most popularly significant in the selection. In turn, VR tours, particularly *Al Zubarah*, *Eye of the Owl - Hieronymus Bosch VR*, and *Historium VR - Relive the history of Bruges*, possess a narrower spectrum of historical authenticity strategies.

Non-interactive immersive videos, while technically simpler, nonetheless, within the analyzed selection, on average, do not lag behind interactive VR games in terms of implemented strategies for ensuring historical authenticity. However, in the case of interactive applications, alongside historical authenticity, one can also speak of behavioral and psychological authenticity (Wackerfuss, 2013, p. 237), which is provided by the ability to perform authentic actions using a virtual body: for example, fighting using a Renaissance Italian sword in *Assassin's Creed Nexus VR* or reloading a rifle in *Sniper Elite VR*. Meanwhile, interactive applications are by definition further from precise reconstruction of the past than non-interactive videos, as the virtual past in the moment in interactive applications is to some extent defined by the actions of the player (Peterson et al., 2013, p. 37), which can be extremely distant from historical accuracy.

Conclusion

Ultimately, to have a tangible impact on collective memory and view of history, the information conveyed by history-related immersive VR apps must not only be authentic, plausible, and inspire trust, but also be relatively well remembered, that is, integrated into users' existing memory structure. Empirical research shows that in the conveyance of declarative knowledge, immersive VR media lag behind other media. The likely reason for this may be hyper-emotionalization, provided by immersive VR technology, which distracts from the perception of factual information. However, in the acquisition of procedural knowledge, immersive VR media, on the contrary, prove to be particularly effective (Mulders et al., 2022, p. 136). This emphasizes the impact primarily of interactive VR applications on collective memory, as it is these applications that allow users to perform virtual actions and thereby acquire procedural knowledge. Fostering the ability to critically perceive such content is one of the tasks of modern historical didactics (Bunnenberg, 2017, p. 120).

Considering that the strategies for ensuring historical authenticity used in interactive immersive VR content are practically indistinguishable from the strategies used in interactive desktop (less-immersive) digital content, particularly in video games, the question arises as to whether the immersive VR technology itself enhances the sense of historical authenticity. To answer this question, an empirical study with several dozen participants is planned within the framework of my PhD research project. The participants are expected to be divided into two groups, which will play similar immersive VR and desktop (less-immersive) video games, specifically *Assassin's Creed Nexus VR* and *Assassin's Creed II Remastered*. After completing the gameplay, the participants will be required to fill out questionnaires and give interviews on the topic of historical authenticity in the tested video games. The results of this

empirical study could be another contribution to the discussion on historical authenticity, plausibility, and trust in history-related VR.

References

- anne frank house. (n.d.). *The Anne Frank House in virtual reality*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://www.annefrank.org/en/about-us/what-we-do/publications/anne-frank-house-virtual-reality/>
- arte. (n.d.a). *Accused #2: Walter Sisulu*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://www.arte.tv/digitalproductions/de/accused2-walter-sisulu/>
- arte. (n.d.b). *Verdammt zu spielen*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://www.arte.tv/digitalproductions/de/verdammt-zu-spielen/>
- Barbot, B., & Kaufman, J. C. (2020). What makes immersive virtual reality the ultimate empathy machine? Discerning the underlying mechanisms of change. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2020.106431>
- BBC. (2017). *Easter Rising: Voice of a Rebel*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://www.bbc.co.uk/taster/pilots/easter-rising-voice-of-a-rebel>
- Bergmann, K. (2000). Personalisierung und Personifizierung. In K. Bergmann (Ed.), *Geschichtsdidaktik. Beiträge zu einer Theorie historischen Lernens*. Wochenschau Verlag, 158-161.
- Buchner, J., & Aretz, D. (2020). Lernen mit immersiver Virtual Reality: Didaktisches Design und Lessons Learned Article, *Zeitschrift MedienPädagogik*, 17, 195-216. <https://doi.org/10.21240/mpaed/jb17/2020.05.01.X>
- Bunnenberg, C. (2017). Digitale Zeitreisen in die Vergangenheit? Computerspiele mit historischen Inhalten und geschichtskulturelles Lernen im Geschichtsunterricht. In S. Assmann, K. Kasper, P. Moormann, & W. Zielinski (Eds.), *Spielend lernen! Computerspiele(n) in Unterricht und Schule*, kopaed verlagsGmbH, 117-126.
- Bunnenberg, C. (2018). Virtuelle Zeitreisen? Public History und Virtual Reality. *Public History Weekly*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.1515/phw-2018-10896>
- Dorr, M. E., Erll, A., Högerle, E., Vickers, P., & Wegner, J. (2019). Introduction: Travel, locatedness, and new horizons in Memory Studies. *Journal of Aesthetics & Culture*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20004214.2019.1690840>
- Frentzel-Beyme, L., & Krämer, N. C. (2023). Historical Time Machines: Experimentally Investigating Potentials and Impacts of Immersion in Historical VR on History Education and Morality. *Technology, Mind and Behavior*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.1037/tmb0000099>

- Giere, D. (2019). *Computerspiele – Medienbildung – historisches Lernen: Zur Repräsentation von Geschichte in Digitalen Spielen*. Wochenschau Verlag.
- Herrera, F., Bailenson, J., Weisz, E., Ogle, E., & Zaki, J. (2018). Building long-term empathy: A large-scale comparison of traditional and virtual reality perspective-taking, *PloS one* 13(10). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0204494>
- Holdenried, J. D., & Trépanier N. (2013). Dominance and the Aztec Empire: Representations in Age of Empires II and Medieval II: Total War. In M. W. Kapell, & A. B. R. Elliott (Eds.), *Playing with the Past: Digital games and the simulation of history*, Bloomsbury Academic, 107-120. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781628928259.ch-007>
- IntoVR. (2017). *Was wollten Sie in Berlin?!*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://intovr.de/2017/05/11/stasi-gefaengnis-360-film-was-wollten-sie-in-berlin/>
- Lewers, E., & Frentzel-Beyme L. (2023). Und was kommt nach der Zeitreise? Eine empirische Untersuchung des Auftauchens aus geschichtsbezogener Virtual Reality. *MedienPädagogik*, 51, 403-429. <https://doi.org/10.21240/mpaed/51/2023.01.26.X>
- Meta. (2016). *Apollo 11 VR*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://www.meta.com/de-de/experiences/pcvr/937027946381272/>
- Meta. (2018a). *Al Zubarah*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://www.meta.com/de-de/experiences/pcvr/1607086019361043/>
- Meta. (2018b). *Titanic VR*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://www.meta.com/de-de/experiences/pcvr/titanic-vr/1490109271079729/>
- Meta. (2019a). *Traveling While Black*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://www.meta.com/experiences/2121787737926354/>
- Meta. (2019b). *Visby Archer*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://www.meta.com/experiences/pcvr/2298826323547241/>
- Meta. (2022). *Warplanes: Battles over Pacific*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://www.meta.com/experiences/3984056454948095/>
- Mulders, M., Buchner, J., & Kerres, M. (2022). Gestaltungsprinzipien für immersive Lernszenarien mit und über Virtual Reality. In V. Pirker, & K. Pišonić (Eds.), *Virtuelle Realität und Transzendenz. Theologische und pädagogische Erkundungen*, Herder, 132-149.
- Mulders, M. (2024). Beyond Comparing Learning Technologies: Experiencing Flow in Virtual Reality. In D. G. Sampson, D. Ifenthaler, P. Isaiás (Eds.), *Smart Learning Environments in the Post Pandemic Era. Cognition and Exploratory Learning in the Digital Age*, Springer, 39-56. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-54207-7_3
- Peaky Blinders: The King's Ransom*. (n.d.). Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://www.peakyblindersthekingransom.com/>

- Peterson, R. D., Miller, A. J., & Fedorko S. J. (2013). The Same River Twice: Exploring Historical Representation and the Value of Simulation in the Total War, Civilization, and Patrician Franchises. In M. W. Kapell, & A. B. R. Elliott (Eds.), *Playing with the Past: Digital games and the simulation of history*, Bloomsbury Academic, 33-48. <http://doi.org/10.5040/9781628928259.ch-002>
- PlayStation Blog. (2023). *PlayStation Store: Top-Downloads 2022*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://blog.de.playstation.com/2023/01/17/playstation-store-top-downloads-2022/>
- Rebellion. (2021). *Sniper Elite VR*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://rebellion.com/ru/games/sniper-elite-vr/>
- Reisner, C. (2013). "The Reality Behind It All Is Very True": Call of Duty: Black Ops and the Remembrance of the Cold War. In M. W. Kapell, & A. B. R. Elliott (Eds.), *Playing with the Past: Digital games and the simulation of history*, Bloomsbury Academic, 247-260. <http://doi.org/10.5040/9781628928259.ch-016>
- Rochat, Y. (2020). A Quantitative Study of Historical Video Games (1981–2015). In A. Lünen, K. J. Lewis, B. Litherland, & P. Cullum (Eds.), *Historia Ludens: The Playing Historian*. Routledge, 3-19. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429345616-1>
- Sabrow, M. (2022). Zeitzeuge. In M. Sabrow, & A. Saupe (Eds.), *Handbuch Historische Authentizität*, Wallstein Verlag, 553-562.
- Salvati, A. J., & Bullinger, J. M. (2013). Selective Authenticity and the Playable Past. In M. W. Kapell, & A. B. R. Elliott (Eds.), *Playing with the Past: Digital games and the simulation of history*, Bloomsbury Academic, 153-168. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781628928259.ch-010>
- Samida, S., Willner, S., & Koch, G. (2016). Doing History – Geschichte als Praxis. In S. Samida, S. Willner, & G. Koch (Eds.), *Doing History: Performative Praktiken in der Geschichtskultur*, Waxmann Verlag, 1-28.
- Santana, D. (2022). Historians as Digital Storytellers: The Digital Shift in Narrative Practices for Public Historians. In S. Noiret, M. Tebeau, & G. Zaagsma (Eds.), *Handbook of Digital Public History*. De Gruyter Oldenbourg, 485-494. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110430295-043>
- Schmidt, S., & Voges, R. (2011). Einleitung. In S. Schmidt, S. Krämer, R. Voges (Eds.), *Politik der Zeugenschaft: Zur Kritik einer Wissenspraxis*, transcript Verlag, 7-20.
- Schmidt, S. (2011). Wissensquelle oder ethisch-politische Figur? Zur Synthese zweier Forschungsdiskurse über Zeugenschaft, In S. Schmidt, S. Krämer, R. Voges (Eds.), *Politik der Zeugenschaft: Zur Kritik einer Wissenspraxis*, transcript Verlag, 47-66.
- Schwan, S. (2022). Virtuelle Realitäten. In M. Sabrow, & A. Saupe (Eds.), *Handbuch Historische Authentizität*, Wallstein Verlag, 536-544.
- Schwarz, A. (2020). Quarry - Playground - Brand. In M. Lorber, & F. Zimmermann (Eds.), *History in Games. Contingencies of an Authentic Past*, transcript Verlag, 25-45.

- Schweppenstette, F. (2020). Interview: Virtuelle Ausflüge in die Geschichte. Ein Gespräch zwischen dem TimeRide-Gründer Jonas Rothe und Christian Bunnenberg über Zeitreisen und digitale Geschichtsvermittlung. *Geschichte für heute*, 13(4), 60-67.
- Sidequest. (2020). *Gladius*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://sidequestvr.com/app/1707/gladius>
- Smirnov, R. (2024). *History-related Immersive VR Apps Database*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://l.rub.de/0c24c8cd>
- Steam. (2016). *Historium VR - Relive the history of Bruges*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from https://store.steampowered.com/app/563830/Historium_VR__Relive_the_history_of_Bruges/
- Steam. (2017a). *Battle of Red Cliffs VR*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from https://store.steampowered.com/app/716400/Battle_of_Red_Cliffs_VR/
- Steam. (2017b). *VR Battleship YAMATO*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from https://store.steampowered.com/app/649620/VR_Battleship_YAMATO/
- Steam. (2018). *Meet the Miner - WDR VR Bergwerk*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from https://store.steampowered.com/app/916130/Meet_the_Miner__WDR_VR_Bergwerk/
- Tang, R., & Wei, L. (2022). Aural Authenticity and Reality in Soundscape of VR Documentary, *Interactive Film & Media Journal*, 2(4), 33-41. <https://doi.org/10.32920/ifmj.v2i4.1644>
- The Farm 51. (2016). *Chernobyl VR Project*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://www.thefarm51.com/eng/projekt/chernobyl-vr-project-2/>
- Ubisoft. (2023). *Assassin's Creed Nexus VR*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://www.ubisoft.com/de-de/game/assassins-creed/nexus-vr>
- Viveport. (2016). *Eye of the Owl - Hieronymus Bosch VR*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://www.viveport.com/apps/fde15a29-142f-4ecc-a966-73cc4d8a9739?hl=>
- Wackerfuss, A. (2013). This Game of Sudden Death: Simulating Air Combat of the First World War. In M. W. Kapell, & A. B. R. Elliott (Eds.), *Playing with the Past: Digital games and the simulation of history*, Bloomsbury Academic, 233-246. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781628928259.ch-015>
- War Remains*. (2021). Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://www.warremains.com/>
- ZDF. (2017). *Gladiatoren im Kolosseum*. Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://vr.zdf.de/gladiatoren/>
- Zimmermann, F. (2018). *Digitale Spiele als historische Erlebnisräume Ein Zugang zu Vergangenheitsatmosphären im Explorative Game*, vwh Verlag Werner Hülsbusch.